

BLENDED LEARNING AND ITS IMPACT ON LEARNERS' LEARNING PROGRESS IN MATHEMATICS

Vanissa Choco H. Lofranco

EdD Department, National Teachers College, Manila, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The basic research aimed to identify learners learning progress in Mathematics through blended learning. There were twenty-two respondents in this study. It is qualitative with descriptive analyses. A self-made survey questionnaire for the factors affecting the learner's progress and Early Grade Mathematics Assessment was used as a tool to measure the current learning ability of the learners in this particular subject. It showed that 32.64% of the items were answered correctly by the respondents from the result of the EGMA. It indicates that not half of the class has prior knowledge of mathematical concepts. In the survey, with a mean of 2.68 (0.16 SD), it manifested that respondents agreed with the factors indicated. It also shows the positive impact of blended learning as they have enough time to understand the lessons during in-person classes. It was recommended to provide manipulative materials for grade one learners who need to learn first with their senses before learning it through abstract.

Keywords: *EGMA, Blended Learning, Learning Progress*

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education released the DepEd Order 17 s. 2022 which stipulated the guidelines on the progressive expansion of the face-to-face classes. It focused on the mechanism of conducting the face-to-face classes ensuring quality and safe implementation of classes. For two years modular distance learning and other educational delivery have been maximized to ensure quality education despite the

change in the education system in our country caused by the pandemic. Currently, teachers and students are in for full in-person classes.

Every student greatly benefits from studying mathematics because it is so valuable in both academic settings and daily life. This is the rationale behind why young pupils should develop their mathematical abilities. Since the majority of first-graders were unable to learn the skill personally during their modular distance learning, they are now moving toward acquiring it personally. In comparison to learning it in class with their classmates, their experience learning it at home is very different. It is a challenging subject to teach, especially as students must first master the ability to use concrete things before moving on to manipulating those objects before utilizing abstract notation. The students were able to engage in mathematics through blended learning. The phase between modular distance learning and in-person learning is known as blended learning. At this point, students might acclimatize to acquiring the various abilities in a different learning environment. However, for students to meet the department's requirements for competencies, teachers had to spend twice as much time teaching this ability. To make Mathematics more effective, communication is essential. Like any other topic, mathematics must be taught and learned by both the teacher and the student to converse successfully (Mulwa, 2015). This subject is the backbone of all advancements in technology and science.

The purpose of this study, which was undertaken by the researcher, was to evaluate the effectiveness of blended learning as a mode of instruction for first-graders at Buko Elementary School. The outcomes of this study will serve as the foundation for the intervention that will be given to learners who have been identified as struggling in mathematics. It will also act as a guide for grades that are using blended learning and have run into a similar problem.

Research Questions

In this basic research, the researcher attempted to evaluate learners' learning progress in mathematics under blended learning; specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the score of the grade 1 learners in Mathematics on their EGMA?
2. What are the factors in learning Mathematics that affect the learning progress of the grade one learners through blended learning?

This fundamental study examined how blended learning affected students' mathematical learning progress. The study is restricted to the variables influencing how well pupils are learning. There are just 22 students in grade 1 at Maanas Elementary School in the Medina District, Misamis Oriental Division. This inquiry is not intended to address other issues that may influence how well pupils are learning mathematics.

METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive and employs quantitative survey analysis. It is categorized as a survey since data was gathered through observation.

According to Bhattacharya & Chetty (2020) descriptive study is a form of study design that seeks to comprehend what is associated with the phenomenon. Data are qualitatively gathered and then quantitatively examined. This technique is used to gather information for the study's current problem. Its primary goal is to convey the current state of affairs.

The 22 first-graders of Maanas Elementary School in the District of Medina, Division of Misamis Oriental for the academic year 2023–2024 are the participants in this study. In this investigation, deliberate sampling was used. Purposive sampling, according to Crossman, 2020, is a non-probability type of sampling that is based on the population's characteristics and the study's goals.

For the participants' welfare, this study adhered to ethical research standards such as parental approval, anonymity and secrecy, and a letter requesting permission to carry out the study in the school. In addition, by carrying out the study appropriately, the participants' rights will be protected, so that the results will be made public.

The participants were given the study questionnaires. After the respondent provided their answers, the researcher then retrieved the questionnaires.

The instrument utilized in this investigation had two components. The first step involved compiling the students' typical results on the diagnostic test. EMRA was utilized during the diagnostic test. and their first-quarter math exam for the academic year 2023-2024. The second component was a 10-item survey questionnaire created by the researcher asking participants about the elements they believed were influencing their progress in learning the subject during blended learning.

In this investigation, the mean, frequency, and standard deviation were the statistical methods used. These were used to provide descriptive statistics to explain the study. Additionally, data from the survey questionnaire was gathered and entered into the SPSS program.

RESULTS

This part presents the discussion of the data that were gathered from the survey. It answers the research questions mentioned in the previous page.

Research Question 1: What is the score of the grade 1 learners in Mathematics on their diagnostic examination?

Diagnostic testing is crucial to determining a student's learning capacities. This allows teachers to assess their students' strengths, weaknesses, aptitudes, and personalities to determine how to adjust their learning strategies so that students can grasp mathematical concepts and improve their skills. It serves as a barometer of the learners' knowledge (Tookoian, 2022) and is used to identify the causes of learning difficulty of the learners.

The table below presents the score of the grade 1 learners in Mathematics on their Early Grade Mathematics Assessment. It is an oral assessment tool used to assess the numeracy and mathematical skills of learners in their early grades. It targets the

foundation of mathematical knowledge (Gandara, 2017). To guide teaching strategies, it is used to ascertain where children are in their mathematical development.

Table 1

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Learners' Score in Mathematics on Their EGMA

Tasks	Frequency	Percentage
Number Identification	9	31.82
Number Discrimination(P1)	8	36.36
Number Discrimination(P2)	9	40.91
Missing Number(1)	6	27.27
Missing Number(2)	6	27.27
Addition(L1)	7	31.82
Addition(L2)	6	27.27
Subtraction(L1)	7	27.27
Subtraction(L2)	6	31.82
Word Problem (P1)	8	36.36
Word Problem (P2)	9	40.91
TOTAL	79	32.64

Research Question 2: What are the factors in learning Mathematics that affect the learning progress of the grade one learners through blended learning?

The capacity of learners to learn is influenced by a variety of circumstances. Depending on the learner's preferred method of learning, it differs from one learner to the next. However, each of these variables has an impact on how well the students are doing. Each learner's progress can be explained by their learning profile. (Hailikari et al., 2016). With blended learning, students have the option of learning in both their homes and at school. They learn from their teachers and their guardians.

The table below presents the distribution of learners' responses to factors affecting their learning progress in Mathematics through blended learning.

Table 2

Mean Distribution of Factors Affecting the Learners' Learning Progress in Mathematics.

Factors	Mean	SD	Description
1. I can easily understand mathematical concept during the blended learning.	2.73	0.46	Agree
2. I receive full support from my parents during modular learning	2.32	0.57	Neutral
3. I have enough time to answer my modules at home.	2.68	0.48	Agree
4. I enjoy active learning during our face-to-face classes	2.36	0.79	Agree
5. I am motivated to understand the lesson in Mathematics.	2.59	0.59	Agree
6. I enjoy using manipulative materials for during our face-to-face classes	2.77	0.43	Agree
7. I receive immediate feedback from my teacher after our tests.	2.73	0.55	Agree
8. I am confident to ask questions from my teachers whenever there are things that I did not understand.	2.64	0.66	Agree
9. I can contact my teacher whenever I need an immediate answer regarding my modules during my modular learning.	2.91	0.29	Agree
10. I understand deeply the lessons through blended learning.	2.86	0.35	Agree
Overall	2.68	0.16	Agree

Legend:1.00-1.66- Disagree; 1.67-2.32-Neutral; 2.33-2.98- Agree

DISCUSSION

Table 1 The table reveals that just half of the students correctly completed the assessment. It is anticipated that the kindergarten kids in grade one will have difficulty with arithmetic because they did not participate in in-person classes and because they are still learning how to use numbers, especially when answering word problems. The majority of the students had not advanced their mathematics knowledge beyond what they had learned in kindergarten. These learners benefit from modular remote learning. The assessment's findings, however, do not apply to all students. Due to several variables, that type of learning delivery method does not support learners' learning progress very well.

Missing numbers, addition, and subtracting numbers at level 2 had a frequency of 6 (27.27%). Students had trouble finding the missing numerals. They find level 2 addition and subtraction to be quite challenging. Even though students were already exposed to these during their kindergarten year, blended or modular online learning is very different from in-person learning. Additionally, Sidik et al. (2021) found that learners did not comprehend the prerequisite material on place value, and addition and subtraction were not yet covered in the time allotted for the lesson. Immediate learning interventions for the learners' learning gaps in this subject were not provided during their modular distance learning, especially for those learners' parents who were reluctant to ask the teacher about the issue.

A frequency of 7 (31,82%) was obtained for addition level one and subtraction level two. Since it was their first lesson on the mathematics topic, students were instructed on how to identify numbers. The first math operations that children learn are addition and subtraction. However, it doesn't occur all at once. Between kindergarten to the fourth grade, students normally learn addition and subtraction in discrete chunks (Drinks, 2022). They were able to recognize numbers, add, and subtract thanks to the blended learning method of delivering education to every learner. They were able to understand the course in person, and the modular exercises helped them apply what they had learned in class. Since this subject was not personally taught to the students over the previous academic year, it is clear that they are struggling, especially since this evaluation was designed to determine the student's current level of mathematical concept knowledge.

Word problem 1 with a frequency of 8 (36.36%), and number discrimination issue 1 with a frequency of 8 (36.36%),. Certain students grasp how to differentiate between numbers with ease, especially those who have mastered number identification. Despite receiving such a high frequency from the class, it is still insufficient because the majority of students chose the incorrect response. These eight students were able to comprehend the word problem with ease and, after carefully examining it, came up with the right answer. They also utilized their fingers for counting. Each of them used a different approach to solve the issue.

With a frequency of 9, or 40.91%, the problems include number identification, number discrimination issue 2, and word problem 2. The results show that students possessed concepts for counting and classifying numbers. If they could recognize numbers, they wouldn't struggle to distinguish between them and could comprehend how to answer word problems. These students must recognize the symbols that correlate to each number to recognize numbers (Cunningham, 2022). Although the majority of students were successful in these skills, the total number of students is still too low, indicating that students must work hard to improve their mathematical abilities and that teachers must effectively communicate the teaching and learning processes to increase student learning.

The learners' learning progress is impacted by several things. Their capacity to pick up new skills and improve on honed ones depends on several variables. These elements, meanwhile, could potentially differ from one student to the next. Depending on how a student interpreted those elements.

The survey's findings in table 2 reveal that, except for remedial classes, the majority of respondents agreed with all of the considerations listed, according to the

questionnaire. However, the overall finding suggested that students agreed on the listed factors.

In factor number 1 "I can easily understand mathematical concepts during the blended learning", respondents agreed, with a mean score of 2.73 (0.46 SD). There is sufficient time for students to comprehend the lesson. In addition to studying it in school, their parents had the time to follow up with them as they also had the opportunity to teach them at home. This method of one-on-one instruction gave their kids the attention they needed to comprehend.

As they have the time to acquire the topic in school and further their learning at home with the aid of their modules, this sort of learning modality enables the students to comprehend the concept in depth. They have plenty of time to critically evaluate the topic they should learn because of this. Teachers can teach mathematics concepts (Manfreda and Hodnik, 20221) and it requires creativity in solving mathematical problems (Chasanah, et al.,2020). As their primary source of education, instructors' creative thinking is essential to helping these students understand mathematical ideas.

In factor number 2 "I receive full support from my parents during modular learning", there will inevitably be parents who are unable to provide their children with their full support given that the mean is 2.32 (0.57SD). Taking into account their family size, line of employment, level of income, and other variables Regarding this assertion, respondents were undecided. Although some parents can provide it to their kids, the majority of respondents fell somewhere in the center.

The assistance of the parents is crucial to the learners' success. They require more instruction to deepen their understanding since the learning they obtain in school is insufficient. For children to see and feel the support from their parents and be encouraged to achieve their best, it is crucial to provide them with the resources they need in school to meet the criteria and to deepen their grasp of mathematics. According to Durisic and Bunijevac 2017, parents' involvement in learners' activities in school has positive impacts as they are motivated to go to school and learn more.

In factor number 3" I have enough time to answer my modules at home." Respondents concurred with a mean of 2.68 (0.48 SD). They had adequate time to respond because their modules were brief and in-depth. They had the opportunity to learn and comprehend the teachings in two separate learning environments, giving them plenty of time to respond with their parents' help.

Their modules serve as extra resources and educational tools. They have plenty of time to research and respond. They are learning more by responding to it. Parents and guardians were constantly urged to help their children with the questions and to adhere to the allotted time for each subject because they were only in the first grade. Parents then played a crucial role in their children's education, especially in the lower grades where students still rely heavily on their teachers for instruction (Ramirez, et al., 2022).

According to Giarla 2022, blended learning allows for variable timetables that can be tailored to each individual, allowing them to learn at their own pace. As they are given ample time to complete the work at home, students have adequate time to respond to their modules. They can complete it on time and turn it in during their in-person classes with the help of their parents and guardians.

In factor number 4 "I enjoy active learning during our face-to-face classesLearners in the first grade appreciate the in-person lessons as well as they enjoy learning with their

peers, respondents agreed, with a mean of 2.36 (0.79) respondents. They must concentrate in class on learning a certain mathematical subject. Additionally, they face challenges, particularly during the activity and assessment periods. They had to work hard to comprehend the teachings and complete the assignments. Even though they had days where they had to complete their modules, learning from home is very different than learning in a classroom.

Inherently more socially active learning methods report much better levels of motivation, engagement, enjoyment, and satisfaction with instruction (Nguyen, et al.2021). It shows that active learning makes learners participate well in the discussions. Through this, they can apply the theories that they are learning in this subject. When they are active, they are more motivated to learn. It is when they can use their critical thinking skills.

In factor number 5 “I am motivated to understand the lesson in Mathematics.” Respondents agreed with a mean of 2.59 (0.59 SD). Due to the numerous opportunities for active learning in this subject, students were encouraged to learn the lesson. With so many enjoyable activities, students were inspired to learn. As additional learning tools, participants were allowed to watch videos that explored the topics in addition to the exercises they completed.

Learners' motivation to learn is influenced by a variety of circumstances. Activities that spark their interests are one of them. In addition to enjoying it better, students will learn more when teachers can relate each activity to the interests of the students.

In factor number 6 “I enjoy using manipulative materials for during our face-to-face classes” respondents agreed, with a mean score of 2.77 (0.43 SD). Particularly for students in lower grades who are still honing their arithmetic abilities, manipulative tools are crucial. Since math is a subject that is relevant to daily life, learners were given manipulative materials during class so they could experience math in the real world. The learners were able to appreciate the lesson and apply it in real-life situations because they had experienced the concept.

The use of manipulatives in the classroom has long been supported by Montessori schools. It has been demonstrated that using these tools makes it easier for students to comprehend the concepts and ideas they are required to learn that day (Furner and Worrell, 2017). Since students need to see and experience mathematics before they can learn it abstractly, manipulative tools are crucial in first-grade mathematics instruction.

In factor number 7 “I receive immediate feedback from my teacher after our tests.” Respondents agreed with a mean score of 2.73 (0.55 SD). For students to understand their strengths and flaws, feedback is important. Teachers can then determine which kids require remediation as a result. Due to their inadequacies, the students were able to recognize that they needed remediation to comprehend the subject. If they don't comprehend the prior topics, they can't comprehend the next issue.

It is crucial to let these students know where they need to develop so that they can take the appropriate steps. Despite their age, students should be self-aware, especially given how difficult it may be to develop numerical skills. Additionally, teachers can encourage students in this way.

In factor number 8 “I am confident to ask questions from my teachers whenever there are things that I did not understand.” Respondents agreed with a mean score of 2.64 (0.66 SD). Students had the opportunity to clarify any concepts they did not grasp

by asking questions, whether in an in-person session or a modular course. Learning was improved in this way. Learners naturally have inquiries about things they don't understand. It is crucial to respond to their inquiries because of this.

Teachers need to instill confidence in their students. In this way, they won't be hesitant to ask their teachers questions and get the answers they need. Building a sense of community among students can inspire them to learn and make them more willing to ask teachers questions. Since the teacher can offer the essential responses, it will encourage the students to desire to learn more.

In factor number 9 "I can contact my teacher whenever I need an immediate answer regarding my modules during my modular learning." Respondents agreed with a mean score of 2.91 (0.29 SD). The teacher was on hand to respond to questions about the lesson regardless of the student's preferred learning style. Giving support to students and parents who lack knowledge of the teachings is crucial, both for the students and the Teaching Observations, Instructional Coaching, 2021). To enable these students to receive the answers to their questions, teachers must be available. It also acts as their teachers' support. Even if teachers are unable to accommodate students right away, it is crucial to offer students time to extend their learning.

In factor number 10 "I understand deeply the lessons through blended learning." With a mean of 2.68(0.16SD), learners were able to deal with these distractions even though there were some in blended learning, especially when they used the modular approach. This is because they had their parents' support and guidance as they progressed in their education and because their parents wanted their kids to develop as learners.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the benefits of blended learning for students at various grade levels, and it has been used in numerous countries. Although we are still learning about it in our country, the pandemic's learning gap has allowed us to gain access to mixed learning delivery modalities.

Conclusions

This study showed that less students received good scores in answering the missing numbers, addition, and subtraction while most of them got great scores in number identification, number discrimination, and word problem. This result shows that these students are facing factors that affects their mathematical learning. Factors such as receiving support from their parents during their blended learning; enjoying active learning during in-person classes; motivated to understand mathematics; receiving feedback from the teacher; and enjoying manipulative materials. The support they receive inside and outside the classroom are necessary for their development. The use of manipulative is necessary because aside from learning, they are also enjoying the process of learning.

Recommendations

Based on the crucial conclusions and debate of this fundamental study, the following recommendations were made.

1. To make every discussion lively and interesting, the Department of Education Misamis Oriental will provide durable manipulative materials and other instructional resources. Every student will benefit from having access to the appropriate materials, which will encourage critical thinking and allow them to use their mathematical talents, particularly their problem-solving abilities, to the fullest.
2. Administrators at the school should develop interventions for students who struggle with math. This will provide students with learning difficulties with specialized activities that will help them learn and fully grasp the idea.
3. Parents and other stakeholders can support students' learning by closely monitoring the daily lessons they are taking. The pupils' learning will advance significantly, and they will also become more driven to learn as a result.
4. Future Researchers should undertake a larger-scale investigation using the same factors to provide more crucial details about the study done in the aforementioned institution.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

For the participants' welfare, this study adhered to ethical research standards such as parental approval, anonymity and secrecy, and a letter requesting permission to carry out the study in the school. In addition, by carrying out the study appropriately, the participants' rights will be protected, so that the results will be made public.

The parents were informed ahead that their children were chosen to become respondents of this study. They were also made aware that they can decline and not allow their children to participate in the study. The respondents were also made aware of their rights and that they can withdraw from being respondents anytime. They were also assured that in conducting this study, they will be free from any form of harm. Plagiarism was strictly avoided. This study is free from bias in interpreting the findings and all of the results from this study is used solely for the purpose of this study only.

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